

Effect of study habits counselling on senior students' achievement in English language

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of study habits counselling on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students achievement in English language in North-west, Benue State, Nigeria. The study adopted a Quasi-experimental design. The population of the study was five thousand, three hundred and twenty nine SS2 students (5,329) of public schools. The sample size for the study was 100 senior secondary school 2 students drawn from intact class of a public school through multi stage sampling technique. Two instruments were used for the collection of data, English Achievement Test (EAT) and Study Habits Counselling Questionnaire (SHCQ). The reliability of the research instruments was established using Lemma co-efficient Alpha. Data was collected and analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the hypotheses. Findings revealed that study habits counselling has significant effect on the academic achievement of secondary school students in English. Study habits counselling has no statistical significant difference in the mean score of male and female students. The study concludes that study habits counselling has effect on the academic achievement of students in English, however, there is no significant difference between male and female. Thus, group guidance should be organized in schools to create awareness on effective study habits. A functional school library should be mounted. Parents and guardians should encourage their children to set up schedules for study. Qualified English teachers should be employed in all secondary schools. Guidance counsellors should include study habits counselling as part of new students' orientation to facilitate effective study habits among new students.

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INTRODUCTION

Every individual on earth have different characters and attitudes which they display on a daily basis (Singh, 2016). These bundles of characters and attitudes expressed by these individual can best be described as their habits. These habits are expressed often on a regular basis and may not be easily changed. There is no doubt that students have different habits which include how they study and relate with others. While some students have schedule of time for their studies, some do not have but study only when the examination approaches. Some attend classes regularly and take notes. While others attend at will. Still, others study in quiet, well ventilated places whereas, others do not mind about the place of studying thereby combining studying and other social life (Singh, 2016). Regardless of the students' habits of study, the parents, teachers and school owners desire is to see that the students have good achievement in their subjects. To actualize this dream, Parents support their wards financially and morally, the school owners provide the needed facilities and employ qualified teachers to teach the students. The teachers on their part adopt different techniques and strategies of teaching to help the students in school (Musingafi & Zebron, 2014).

Despite support of parents, school owners and teachers, students cannot achieve well if they have bad study habits. The students need effective study habits because study habits seems to inform a person how much he can learn and how far he wants to go and the extent to acquire. Study habits can be described as the attitudes displayed in the process of learning or actions shown after learning a thing. It may also be viewed as those strategies, which a learner applies in the process of acquiring skills, ideas and knowledge. Crow and Crow as cited in Onuekwe, (2015) assert that study habits include plan/place, a definite timetable, and taking brief and well-organized notes. Ayodele and Adebisi, (2015) and Good in Mohta, (2018) explained study habits as the student's way of studying whether systematic, efficient or inefficient. This means, study habits involve factors that facilitate the study process such as sound study routines which include how often a student attend classes, review the material, self-evaluation, self-discipline, planning their studies and studying in a conducive environment.

Study habits may be effective or ineffective. Effective study habits requires students attending all classes, managing their time, reviewing their notes daily, reading topics before entering classes, have discussions with teachers, read material to improve their background, ask questions in class, avoid a last minutes cram session, avoid postponement of assignment and sleep well the night before exams commences (Ebele & Olofu, 2017). It also requires schedule of time to allocate certain length of time to each subject and other activities depending on the difficulty of each subject and the value of other programmes (Umaru, Terhemba, Bitrus & Habu, 2013). Ineffective study habits on the other hand can make the processes of knowledge acquisition cumbersome, painful and difficult (Ebele & Olofu, 2017). Study habits are not acquired innately but come from training, practice and exposure. Sawar, Bashir, Khan, & Khan, (2009) opined that high achievers at Secondary School had better orientation, study habits and study attitude than the low achievers. Therefore, there is a need for intervention on the study habits of the students through effective study habits counselling because students who lack effective and efficient means of studying may be travelling on a vehicle that is not sound and may crash.

Many students who are ineffective in their study habits cannot plan their time for various school activities, they absent themselves from school at will and when they are not present in school, they cannot take effective notes in addition to neglect of library (Uba & Bulus, 2014). Simon, (2015) examined the effect of study habits on the academic achievement of students and the result showed a significant effect of study skills training between secondary school students exposed to counselling and the control group in their academic achievement. Study habits are skills that are important for students to learn, practice and develop. These study habits can be learnt through teaching, discussions and counselling because a behaviour that is stimulated over a regular period is likely to be repeated. Study habits counselling is an interaction or discussion between the counsellor and the students on how to improve their study habits or how to develop effective study habits. It is conducted in an agreed venue and time for the benefit of students. Robinson as cited in Nsini and Emeya, (2015) admits that the keys to better learning and academic achievement in secondary schools are good study habits counselling. Study habits

counselling programme in schools guide students in study habits thoroughly by enabling them succeed in their secondary school education (Modo, Sanni, Uwah & Mogbo 2013).

Students can benefit if effective study habits counselling is organized in schools because planned study habits counselling motivate students to explore, ask questions and solve problems that confront them (Ogbodo, 2010). Because of the relevance of study habits counselling, Narahari and Tewari, (2015) recommend mandatory study habits counselling for all secondary schools because good study habits counselling leads to quality academic achievement in schools (Sherafat & Murthy, 2016).

Academic achievement can be viewed as quantity of students' measure of performance expressed in scores. In other words, the marks obtained in assignments, tests, and examinations (National policy on Education, 2004). The academic achievement can be measured after a period of studies in meeting short or long-term goals in education. Onuekwe, (2015) opined that study habits and academic achievement of secondary school students are related. There is no agreement on the relationship between academic achievement and study habits of male and female students. Odiri, (2015) revealed that female students tend to have better study habits than their male counterparts while Ajai and Imoko, (2015) found that there is no significant difference in academic achievement scores between male and female students and that both are capable of competing in academic achievement in English language. Poor academic achievements in English Language in Benue State have been attributed to ineffective study habits (Singh, 2016). Mathematics on the other hand is a main subject which is important and useful for development in every country and it is also the backbone of students to achieve and develop the skills in reasoning and thinking level (Musa & Garba, 2019). English language achievement in Benue State is unstable and persistently poor in West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and could continue if nothing is done (Musa & Dauda, 2014). Sometimes, students who are intelligent do not perform well despite the good teachings (Osa-Edoh & Alutu, 2012). There is therefore the need to look at the effort of the students. These efforts are the study habits which Uba and Bulus, (2014) pointed out but were neglected.

The ignorance of good study habits seem to have resulted in negligence of visits to the library, mismanagement of time, truancy and school dropouts. Study habits counselling was recommended by Ogbodo, (2010) but it was not recognized in the school timetable, talk more of planning to practice it. These study habits counselling include; time management, class attendance, note taking, organization of study area, in addition to concentration, reading and use of library. Time management is a skill that every student should not only know but should also practice. It involves setting of goals and priorities and being organized in using time. Time management can be possible when we set and prioritize our goals in every activity we intend to do. Time management involves scheduling of time for all the students' activities which may be daily, weekly or monthly. Attendance has been a subject of debate because learning cannot take place when students are absent from classes. Attendance may be described as the physical presence and actual participation in work and other class activities in the school. Cheung, (2009) argued that students' performance is better when class attendance is higher. Attendance improves academic achievement while absence is responsible for low achievement (Sawar, Bashir, Khan, & Khan, 2009). Some students are present in the class but never engage in class activity like note taking. Note taking involves the writing of important points during personal studies and during the class lessons when the teacher teaches. It may also be the collection of work samples solved by the teacher and the ones studied personally by the students and in group. Padurath, Nagowah, Sungkur, Moloo and Chinia, (2013) stated that note taking is an effective study technique that makes the students to understand and remember what they learn in the class. Notes may be written to safeguard important information and for guide and it could be personal new ideas developed during reading and lessons. Students may be present in class, take down good notes but may fail to study at the right place. A good study place should be well ventilated, quiet, and free from distraction with good light, good chairs and tables.

Study habits' counselling was used in testing achievement because English Language is a core subject needed by all students. In addition, learning of English in one class is dependent on the previous one learnt. It demands indebt studies and practice. This accounted for why the researchers decide to find out the effect of study habits counselling on Senior Secondary School Students' achievement in English Language in North-West, Benue State - Nigeria using English syllabus namely; Concord and agreement, Parts of Speech, Phrases and Clauses and

study habits counselling in time management, class attendance, note taking, study area including general principle of studying and examination preparation. If students develop good study habits, they are bound to perform remarkably well in their academic achievement. Good study habits make students to study their notes daily, asks questions in class, avoid a last minutes cram session, and sleep well the night before exams commences. It makes students to allocate certain time to each subject depending on the difficulty. It motivates students to explore, avoid procrastination, goes to school on time, take notes including rehearsing their notes and attend classes regularly. It also enables the students to select good environment for study because the condition of a place of study can help the students concentrate or get confused.

Despite the relevance of good study habits, there is no provision in the school timetable on how to help ignorant ones on how to study and those with ineffective study habits. Many students find it difficult to plan time schedule for their studies and other programmes because it's hard for them to follow it. Counsellors did not include study habits counselling as part of new students orientation, talk more of organizing training in it. The students lack basic note taking skills and they are rarely taught how to take effective notes by teachers. The administrators and teachers seem to pay less attention to the study-habit needs of the students. The ignorance and negligence of effective study habits may no doubt be unconnected to truancy by students, negligence of visits to the library, lack of time schedule for studies including neglect of note taking, school dropout and persistent poor achievement in English Language in West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) respectively. The poor performance may continue if nothing is done, especially as the successes of students do not depend only on their ability and intelligence but also on their efforts in studying. This accounted for why the researcher undertakes to investigate the effect of study habits counselling on the senior students' achievement in English Language in the North-West of Benue State - Nigeria.

Objectives

The aim of this study is to find out the effect of study habits-counselling on Senior Secondary School 2 student's achievement in English Language in the North-West of Benue State - Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

1. Determine the mean achievement scores of students who received study habits counselling in English Language.
2. Determine the mean achievement scores of students who did not receive study habits counselling in English Language.
3. Determine the difference in mean achievement scores in English Language between students who received and those who did not receive study habits counselling in English Language.
4. Determine the difference in mean achievement scores in English Language between male and female students who received study habits counselling and those who did not receive study habits counselling in English Language.

METHODS

Research design

Research design refers to the overall strategy that researchers choose to integrate different components of the study in a coherent and logical way. The research design for this study is pre-test and post-test design of Quasi-experiment. It is an experiment where measurements are taken both before and after treatment (Dela Fuente, 2021). The design involves the manipulation of independent variables but participants are not assigned randomly (Kolo 2003). This design is germane in this study because this research was carried out in a classroom where classes are intact. Secondly, the school authority might not allow school classes to be altered for the sake of research. In addition, the students may not easily fake their behaviour since intact classes are used and are less aware of an experiment being conducted on them. To ensure equivalent at the beginning of the study, the researcher administered pre-test to the students and the scores were analyzed using analysis of covariance technique to

compensate for the absence of equivalency between the groups. With this design, the findings generalized on the effect of study habits counselling on the academic achievements of students in English Language.

The study area

Benue State is one of the North Central States in Nigeria with a population of about 4,253,641 in 2006 Census. The State was created in 1976, among the 7 States created at that time. The State derives its name from the Benue River, which is the second largest river in Nigeria. The State borders Nasarawa State in the North, Taraba State in the East, Enugu State to the South-West, Kogi State to the West, Ebonyi and Cross-Rivers States to the South; and has an international border with Cameroon to the South-East. It is inhabited predominantly by the Tiv, Idoma, Igede and Etulo peoples. Its capital is Makurdi. Benue is a rich Agricultural region; popularly grown crops include: Oranges, Mangoes, Sweet-Potatoes, Cassava, Soya-beans, Guinea-corn, Flax, Yams, Sesame, Rice, Ground-nuts and Palm-trees.

Population of the study

The research design for this study is quasi experimental design (it uses pre and post test). The population of this study is five thousand, three hundred and twenty nine SS2 students (5,329) in Benue North-West. (Source: School Services Department, Ministry of Education, Makurdi). SS2 Students were chosen because they are preparing for Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) by West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) respectively. The learning of good study habits can make the students learn and practice effective study habits before facing external examinations. Benue North-West was chosen because it comprised the state capital and anything learnt in the state capital can be easily model in other parts of the state,

Sample and sampling technique

The sample for this study was 100 SS2 students drawn from an intact class. A multi stage sampling technique was used for the selection of sample because at different stages, different sampling technique was employed. Multi-stage sampling is a sampling technique requiring the use of several stages of sampling elements of the population. In this study, the sampling stages include sampling of Ministry of Education, Area Inspectorate Office, sampling of school and purposive use of intact class for the study. Firstly, a random sampling technique was used to select one Area Inspectorate Office from the five Area Inspectorate Offices of Ministry of Education in Benue North-West. Secondly, a simple random sampling technique of slip of the papers method was used to select a school from the Area Inspectorate Office chosen. In this method, the name of each school in the Area Inspectorate Office was written on slip of papers. The slip was folded and after thorough reshuffling in a bag; the researcher employed the assistance for the picking of a school. Finally, intact class of two streams was used as experimental and control group respectively. This method and sample is necessary for this study because it does not disrupt normal class register. It also prevents faking of behaviour by the students since they are not aware that an experiment is been carried out on them. To give pre-test, the researcher based the test on their syllabi so that he can have equivalent scores between control and experimental group.

Instruments for data collection

Two instruments were used for the collection of data from the respondents namely; English Language Achievement Test and Study Habits Counselling. The English Language Achievement Test has pre-test and posttest. The Pre-test consisted of 25 objective questions adopted from 2019 National Examination Council (NECO) (Appendix A). The essence was to determine the ability of students in English Language. The post-tests items are the same items (twenty-five objective questions adopted from 2019 NECO (Appendix B) presented in the pre-test but were re-arranged before administration. The essence of the post-tests was to determine the score difference of students in Mathematics between experimental and control groups. The answers to pre-tests and post-tests were both scored in the scale of 0-100% and every correct answer was +4. Study Habits Counselling is a module of

training by the counsellor to the students on how to develop and practice effective study habits. It is specifically designed to train students on time management schedule, class attendance, note taking including study environment and general principles of studying and preparation for examination. The training is given to the students after pre-test before post-test. The aim is to make the students learn, practice and develop effective study habits.

Validation of the instrument

The instruments were validated by three experts. One from Guidance and counselling, one from Test and Measurement, all from the Department of Educational Foundations and General Studies, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi and one from Benue State Senior Secondary Schools and their input were reflected in the work. To ascertain the validity of the instrument on English Language Achievement Test (pre-test and post-test), the researcher subjected the instruments to a table of specification in order to ensure that the items covered major topics of SS2 syllabi accurately (Appendix E). To ensure the validity of the instrument on study habits counselling, the researcher subjected the items to scrutiny by the experts and their input was reflected in the work.

Reliability of the instrument

Test-re-test reliability of English Language Achievement Test (pre-test and post-test) instrument was established by administering it twice to thirty (30) Senior Secondary School two (SS2) students in Makurdi LGA, of Benue State who were not part of the main study but have the same characteristics with the main sample of the study. The purpose was to ensure that the tests are reliable. The pre-test was given to the students and after one week of study habits instructions by the researcher, the post-test was administered. The data obtained from English Language Achievement Test was analyzed using Lemma co-efficient Alpha and the analyses yielded a coefficient Alpha of 0.6335 and 0.7335 respectively indicating that the instrument used was reliable and consistent (Appendix D).

Data collection

Three stages were involved in data collection namely, pre-treatment, treatment and post-treatment. In pre-treatment, the researcher with the help of his research assistant administered English Language Achievement Test (pre-test) to the students after an instruction. The achievement test takes a period of one hour thirty minutes (1hr: 30 min) after which the answers were collected for marking. The treatment was forty (40) minutes of study habits counselling twice a week for a period of four weeks to the experimental group only. The treatment is a form of group discussion with the students on their study habits, which involves their time management, note taking, class attendance, study environment and examination preparation. The control groups were not given any study habits counselling. Post treatment is the re-administration of English Language Achievement Test to both experimental and control groups after study habits counseling of the experimental group. The Post-test takes a period of one hour thirty minutes (1hr: 30 min) after which the answers were collected for marking. The scores were compared between the experimental and control groups to establish the differences between the groups.

Experimental procedure

Four stages are involved in administering the instruments to the respondents as follows:

Stage one

The researcher visits the sampled school and seeks permission from the principal to use his students twice a week for four weeks. He told the principal that the purpose of coming to the school twice a week was to organize a study habits counselling for the students as his research. The researcher consulted the school counsellor to serve as assistant. The researcher explained to the assistant the purpose and objectives of the study and enlightened the assistant on how the pre-test; study habits counselling and post-test were to be conducted.

Stage two

Both the experimental and control groups were given pre-test in English Language syllabi namely; Phrases and Clauses, Parts of Speech and Comprehensions. The instrument was administered after an instruction to the students. The students were given one hour thirty minutes (1hr: 30 min) after which it was collected.

Stage three

Study habits counselling was not given to the students in control group while the experimental group received study habits counselling in time management, class attendance, note taking, study environment including preparation for examination. It was organized in eight sessions and the students were permitted to ask questions any time of the session and answers were given to them.

Stage four

Both the experimental group and control group were given the post-test in English Language in the following topics: Phrases and Clauses, Parts of Speech and Comprehensions for a period of one hour thirty minutes (1hr: 30 min), and their scripts were collected, marked and analyzed respectively.

Data analysis technique

Data collected were subjected to both inferential and descriptive statistics. In answering the research questions, descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used while inferential statistics of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The reason is that ANCOVA can help to compensate for lack of equivalency between the groups.

RESULTS

Table 1. Mean Score achievement of English Language Student who did not receive study habits counselling

Group	N	Pre-ENG Mean	SD	Post-ENG Mean	SD	Mean Gain
Control Group	50	39.64	13.01	46.32	10.93	6.68

Source: Field work (2021)

In Table 1: the result shows the mean achievement scores of students that did not received study habits counselling. The result shows that the pre-test, had a mean of 39.64, and SD of 13.01 while the post test result shows a mean of 46.32 and SD of 10.93. The mean gain of the control group is 6.68.

Table 2. Mean Achievement scores of students who received study habits counseling in English Language

Group	N	Pre-ENG Mean	SD	Post-ENG Mean	SD	Mean Gain
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Experimental	50	41.52	13.39	54.40	12.12	12.88
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Source: Field work (2021)

Table 2 revealed the mean scores of students who were exposed to study habits counselling. The result shows that the pre-test had a mean of 41.52, and SD of 13.39 while the post-test had a mean of 54.40 and SD of 12.12 with a mean gain of 12.88.

Table 3. Mean academic achievement scores of male and female students who received study habits counselling and those who did not receive study habits counselling

Group	N	Pre-BAT Mean	SD	Post-BAT Mean	SD	Mean Gain
MALE	50	45.06	14.68	51.17	11.47	6.11
FEMALE	50	44.92	13.94	50.50	12.84	5.58
Mean Difference		0.14		0.675		
Total	100					

Source: Field work (2021)

The result in table 3 shows the mean achievement scores of male and female students exposed to study habits counselling and those not exposed to study habits counselling. The result shows that the male students exposed to study habits counselling has a pre-test mean of 45.06 and SD of 14.68 while post-test has a mean of 51.17 and SD of 11.47 with mean gain of 6.11. The mean for female pre-test has a mean of 44.92 and SD 13.94 while post- test has a mean of 50.50 and SD 12.84 with a mean gain of 5.5, having a mean difference of 0.14 for pre-test and 0.67 for post-test respectively.

Table 4: Mean difference of students who received study habits counselling and those who did not receive study habits counselling

Groups	N	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Control	50	39.64	13.01	46.32	10.93
Experimental	50	41.52	13.39	54.40	12.12
Mean Diff.		1.88		8.08	
N Total	100				

Source: Field work (2021)

The result on table 4 shows the mean difference between the control and experimental group. The pre-test has the mean difference of 1.88 and post-test has the mean difference of 8.08. This shows that the experimental group performance is better than the control group performance.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance of students who received study habits counselling and those who did not receive study habits counselling

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	5.147 ^a	1	5.147	25.408	.000
Intercept	41.370	1	41.370	204.218	.000
PreTest	5.147	1	5.147	25.408	.000
Groups	19.853	98	.203	25.408	.000
Error	250.000	100	5.147		
Total	25.000	99			
Corrected Total	5.147 ^a	1			

Source: Field work (2021)

The result of the Analysis of Covariance in Table 5 shows that the P-value of 0.00 is less than the 0.05 level of significant at 98 degree of freedom. Therefore the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected. This shows that the test is significant. This implies that there is a statistical significant difference in the mean academic achievement scores of students who received study habits counselling and those who do not receive study habits counselling.

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance of female and male students who received study habits counselling and those who did not receive study habits counselling

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	.001 ^a	1	.001	.002	.961
Intercept	20.105	1	20.105	78.813	.000
PreTest	.001	1	.001	.002	.961
Gender	24.999	98	.255	.002	.961
Error	250.000	100	.001		
Total	25.000	99			
Corrected Total	.001 ^a	1			

Source: Field work (2021)

The result of the Analysis of covariance in table 6 shows that the P-value of 0.96 is greater than the 0.05 level of significant at 98 degree of freedom. Therefore the null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. This shows that the test is not significant. This implies that there is no statistical significant difference in the mean scores of male and female students who received study habits counselling and those who did not receive study habits counselling.

DISCUSSIONS

From the analysis of the result, the findings revealed that study habits had significant effect on the academic achievement of students in English Language in Benue State. The result negate the findings of Egbo, (2015) who found out that study habits counselling alone has no significant relationship with academic performance of National Certificate of Education (NCE) 2 students of Enugu state. The result agrees with the findings of Umaru, Terhemba,

Bitrus and Habu, (2013) whose result revealed that, study habits counselling techniques has a significant effect on academic performance of students. The result also agrees with the findings of Mohta, (2018) who revealed counselling as an effective intervention in developing study habits of students.

The result is in consonance with the findings of Adefokun and Mbashir, (2017) who found that there is significant correlation among the variables of time management, note taking and academic achievement. The findings also agrees with the result of Sakirudeen and Sanni, (2015) who found out that there is a significance relationship between note taking, students' use of library, time allocation for study and students' academic performance in Mathematics in senior secondary school two (SS2) in Uyo, Local Education Council. The result of the findings negate the result of Musa and Garba, (2019) who revealed that study habits was negatively related to students performance in selected secondary schools in Makurdi metropolis and the relationship is not statistically significant. The result also agrees with the findings of Osa-Edoh and Alutu, (2012) who revealed that there is a high correlation or relationship between student's habits and student's academic performance. The result also negates the findings of Lalhruaitluangi and Lallianzuali, (2020) who revealed that there is no significant relationship between study habits and academic achievement of high school students in Lunglei District.

Also the result is in consonance with the result of Odiri, (2015) who found out that there is significant relationship between students' study habits and Mathematics achievement in Delta central senatorial district of Delta state, Nigeria while the result also negates the findings of Singh and Kaur, (2020) who revealed a negative correlation between study habits and academic performance in the city of Ludhiana. The result also negate the findings of Bentill, Esia -Donkoh and Ghanney, (2018) who revealed that study habits significantly accounted for 44% variance in student's academic performance. Note taking and time management made unique significant contribution to academic performance among public Junior High schools in Ekunfi District in the central region of Ghana. While the result of the findings in the research hypothesis two is in consonance with the result of Singh and Kaur, (2020) who found that there is no significant difference in the academic achievement between the male and female students. However, the result negates the findings of Mohammed and Mohammed, (2018) who found that differences in academic achievement with respect to gender were found to be significant.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that Study Habits Counselling has effect on the academic achievement of students in English Language. Students within the study area have good study habits. The study also concludes that there is no significant difference between study habits of male and female secondary school students in academic achievement in English Language.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made. Group guidance should be organized in schools by professional counsellors in order to create awareness on effective study habits. A well-equipped functional school library should be mounted in all secondary schools. By so doing, students would be motivated to utilize the library resource which is a good study place. Parents and guardians should encourage their children to set up schedules for study, monitor the schedules and give their children enough time to study at home. The teachers should teach students how to take notes during personal and group studies as well as every lesson. By so doing, the students would develop good habits of note taking and this could lead to good academic achievement. Guidance/counsellors should include study habits counselling as part of new students orientation to facilitate effective study habits among students. Qualified English Language teachers should be employed in all secondary schools. If this is done, students would acquire enough knowledge, ideas and skills on how to tackle English Language problems and this would improve their academic achievement in this subject.

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